

Introduction

Q1. Information sheet for research project “AI coding tools in Software Engineering”

Introduction

You have been invited to take part in research project AI coding tools in Software Engineering, because you are software developer from non-English-speaking countries who actively write code as part of your job. We believe your experiences will greatly benefit this research intending to uncover both benefits and limitations developers face with the increasing integration of AI technology like autocomplete, and code suggestions.

Participation in this research project is voluntary: the decision to take part is up to you. Before you decide to participate we would like to ask you to read the following information, so that you know what the research project is about, what we expect from you and how we deal with processing your personal data. Based on this information you can indicate via the consent declaration whether you consent to take part in this research project and the processing of your personal data.

You may of course always contact the [XXXXXXXXXXXX] via XXXXXXXXXXXX, if you have any questions, or you can discuss this information with people you know.

Purpose of the research

This research project will be managed by dr. [XXXXXXXXXXXX]. The purpose of this research project is to understand the perspectives of non-native English-speaking software developers on the emerging role of AI coding assistants such as GitHub Copilot and TabNine in the development process.

What will taking part in the research project involve?

You will be taking part in a research project in which we will gather information by: Surveys: a questionnaire about AI coding tools in Software Engineering which you can fill in in writing This study will be completely anonymous, and the data obtained from the study will not be traceable to you. For your participation in this research project you will not be compensated.

Potential risks and inconveniences

Your participation in this research project does not involve any physical, legal or economic risks. You do not have to answer questions which you do not wish to answer. Your participation is voluntary. This means that you may end your participation at any moment you choose by letting the researcher know this. You do not have to explain why you decided to end your participation in the research project. Ending your participation will have no disadvantageous consequences for you. If you decide to end your participation during the research, the data which you already provided up to the moment of withdrawal of your consent will be used in the research. Do you wish to end the research, or do you have any questions and/or complaints? Then please contact the [XXXXXXXXXXXX] via [XXXXXXXXXXXX].

Confidentiality of data

The raw and processed research data will be retained for a period of 5 years. Ultimately after expiration of this time period the data will be either deleted or anonymized so that it can no longer be connected to an individual person. The research data will, if necessary (e.g. for a check on scientific integrity) and only in anonymous form be made available to persons outside the research group. This research project was assessed and approved on [07/05/2024] by the ethical review committee of [XXXXXXXXXXXX].

Acknowledgements

Consent form for participation

Q2. Consent form for participation

By signing this consent form I acknowledge the following:

I am sufficiently informed about the research project through a separate information sheet. I have read the information sheet and have had the opportunity to ask questions. These questions have been answered satisfactorily.

I take part in this research project voluntarily. There is no explicit or implicit pressure for me to take part in this research project. It is clear to me that I can end participation in this research project at any moment, without giving any reason. I do not have to answer a question if I do not wish to do so.

Q3. I have read and understand the information above.

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

Q4. I want to participate in this study and continue with the survey

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

SD Experience**Q5. What languages do you primarily use?**

- Python (1)
- C / C++ (2)
- Java (3)
- C# (4)
- JavaScript (5)
- PHP (6)
- Visual Basic (7)

Q6. Have you used AI coding tool in software development?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

AI Tools**Q7. Which AI coding tools have you used?**

- Amazon CodeWhisperer (1)
- GitHub Copilot (2)
- TabNine (3)

- OpenAI Codex API (5)
- Code generation tool specific to my organization that is trained on our proprietary code (6)
- Other (4) (please specify):

Q8. How often do you use code generation tools in your software development work?

	Often (once daily) (1)	Sometimes (weekly) (2)	Rarely (monthly) (3)	I have tried this tool before, but gave up. (5)	I don't know this tool. (4)
Amazon CodeWhisperer (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
GitHub Copilot (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Tabnine (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
OpenAI Codex API (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Code generation tool specific to my organization that is trained on our proprietary code (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q9. Why do you use code generation tools in software development?

Very important (1)	Important (2)	Moderately important (3)	Slightly important (4)	Not important at all (5)
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To finish my programming tasks faster. (6)

To have an autocomplete or reduce the amount of keystrokes I make. (1)

To skip needing to go online to find specific code snippets, programming syntax, or API calls I'm aware of, but can't remember. (2)

To discover potential ways or starting points to write a solution to a problem I'm facing. (3)

To find an edge case for my code I haven't considered. (5)

To collaborate with another person who writes code in a different programming language than me. (7)

Other (4)

Q10. How often the following reasons are why you have trouble understanding code created by code generation tools.

	Always (1)	Often (2)	Sometimes (3)	Rarely (4)	Never (5)
The generated code uses APIs or methods I don't know. (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
The generated code contains too many control structures (e.g., loops, if-else statements). (4)	<input type="radio"/>				
The generated code is too long to read quickly. (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
Other (3)	<input type="radio"/>				

Q11. How often the following reasons are why you find yourself giving up on code created by code generation tools.

	Always (1)	Often (2)	Sometimes (3)	Rarely (4)	Never (5)
I don't understand the generated code well enough to use it. (1)	<input type="radio"/>				
The generated code is too complicated. (8)	<input type="radio"/>				
The generated code doesn't perform the action I want it to do. (2)	<input type="radio"/>				

The generated code doesn't meet functional or non-functional (e.g., security, performance) requirements that I need. (9)	<input type="radio"/>				
The generated code contains too many defects. (3)	<input type="radio"/>				
The generated code's style doesn't match my project's. (4)	<input type="radio"/>				
The generated code uses an API I know, but don't want to use. (5)	<input type="radio"/>				
The generated code uses an API I don't know. (6)	<input type="radio"/>				
Other (7)	<input type="radio"/>				

Q12. How often you experience the following scenarios when you get code from a code generation tool?

	Always (1)	Often (2)	Sometimes (3)	Rarely (4)	Never (5)
I use the code created by a code generation tool as-is. (6)	<input type="radio"/>				

I successfully incorporate the code created by a code generation tool by changing the generated code. (5)

I successfully incorporate the code created by a code generation tool by changing the code or comments around it and regenerating a new suggestion. (8)

When a code generation tool outputs something I don't want, I'm able to modify it to something I want. (2)

I give up on incorporating the code created by a code generation tool and write the code myself. (4)

Q13. How often do you use the following methods to evaluate the generated code?

Always (1) Often (2) Sometimes (3) Rarely (4) Never (5)

Consulting API documentation (1)

Compilers, type checkers, in-IDE syntax checkers, or linters (2)	<input type="radio"/>				
Executing the generated code (3)	<input type="radio"/>				
Quickly checking the generated code for specific keywords or logic structures (4)	<input type="radio"/>				
Examining details of the generated code's logic in depth (5)	<input type="radio"/>				
Other (6)	<input type="radio"/>				

Q14. Describe the types of situations in which you are most successful in using code generation tools in your software development.

Q15. Describe the strategies you use to get code generation tools to generate the best answers for you.

Q16. How much do you rely on or trust the code provided by these tools?

- Do not rely at all (1)
- Rely slightly (2)
- Somewhat rely (3)
- Rely significantly (4)

Completely rely (5)

AI comments

Q17. What is your general opinion about the role of AI in software development?

Q18. Do you see these tools as assisting human developers or replacing them?

Q19. How do you feel about the future capabilities of AI for writing code?

Q20. How long have you been a software developer?

- Less than 1 year (1)
- 1 – 2 years (2)
- More than 3 years (3)

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